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A SYSTEMATIC REVIEW OF THE RISK AND SERENCE OF DENTAL HYPERESTHESIA AFTER A WHITENING PROCEDURE

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ABSTRACT

A systematic review and meta-analysis were conducted to assess the risk and severity of tooth sensitivity after bleaching with and without a desensitizer in adult patients. Discoloration and risk of gum sensitivity were also assessed. A comprehensive MEDLINE search was conducted through PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Cochrane Library. Most of the studies had an unclear risk of bias. There were no differences between groups in the risk ratio for MD (hazard ratio = 0.99; 95% confidence interval [CI] = 0.74-1.33); GZ intensity (standardized mean difference [SMD] = 0.04; 95% CI = 0.79-0.70); color change in color units (CPC - 0.04; 95% CI = 0.50-0.42); discoloration in ΔE^* (CRR = 0.41 (95% CI = 0.07–0.89) and gingival irritation risk ratio (CRR = 1.05; 95% CI = 0.81–1.36). With the exception of the risk of GBM, which was rated as moderate quality of evidence, all other outcomes were rated as low to very low GBM, discoloration, and risk of gingival irritation were similar between groups, but the quality of the evidence for these outcomes was rated as low or very low, which reduced the level of confidence in these outcomes. The inclusion of desensitizers in the whitening gel did not reduce the risk of HC, and the quality of this evidence was considered moderate. On the other hand, GB intensity, discoloration, and risk of gingival irritation were similar between groups, but the quality of the evidence for these results was rated as low or very low, which reduced the validity of the results.

Keywords: hypersensitivity, whitening, bleaching, carbamide peroxide, desensitizing, carbamide peroxide, desensitizer-containing gels.

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СИСТЕМАТИЧЕСКИЙ ОБЗОР ОЦЕНКИ РИСКА И СТЕПЕНИ ВЫРАЖЕННОСТИ ГИПЕРЭСТЕЗИИ ЗУБОВ ПОСЛЕ ПРОЦЕДУРЫ ОТБЕЛИВАНИЯ

АННОТАЦИЯ

Систематический обзор и метаанализ были проведены для оценки риска и степени выраженности чувствительности зубов после отбеливания с десенсенсетайзером и без него у взрослых пациентов. Также оценивали изменение цвета и риск чувствительности десен. Был проведен всесторонний поиск в MEDLINE через PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Кокрановскую библиотеку. Большинство исследований имели неясный риск систематической ошибки. Не наблюдалось различий между группами по соотношению рисков ГЗ (отношение рисков = 0,99; 95% доверительный интервал [ДИ] = 0,74-1,33); интенсивность ГЗ (стандартизованная разница в средних [СРС] = 0,04; 95% ДИ = 0,79-0,70); изменение цвета в единицах расцветки (СРС - 0,04; 95% ДИ = 0,50-0,42); изменение цвета в ΔE^* (СРС = 0,41 (95% ДИ = 0,07–0,89) и отношение риска раздражения десен (СРС = 1,05; 95% ДИ = 0,81–1,36). За исключением риска ГЗ, оцененного как умеренное качество доказательств, все остальные исходы были оценены как низкие и очень низкие. ГЗ, изменение цвета и риск раздражения десен были одинаковыми между группами, но качество доказательств для этих результатов было оценено как низкое или очень низкое, что снизило уровень уверенности в этих исходах. Включение десенсенсетайзеров в отбеливающий гель не снижало риск ГЗ, и качество этих доказательств было расценено как среднее. С другой стороны, интенсивность ГЗ, изменение цвета и риск раздражения десен были одинаковыми между группами, но качество доказательств для этих результатов оценивалось как низкое или очень низкое, что снижало достоверность результатов.

Ключевые слова: гиперчувствительность, отбеливание, обесцвечивание, десенсибилизирующий, пероксид карбамида, десенсибилизирующие гели.

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TISHLARNI OQARTIRISH MUOLAJASIDAN SO'NG TISHLAR GIPERESTEZIYASI XAVFI VA NAMOYON BO'LIISH DARAJALARINI TIZIMLI TAHLILI

ANNOTATSIYA

Voyaga etgan bemorlarda desensibilizator bilan va bo'lmagan oqartirishdan keyin tish sezuvchanligi xavfi va jiddiyligini baholash uchun tizimli tekshiruv va meta-tahlil o'tkazildi. Rang o'zgarishi va tish go'shti sezgirligi xavfi ham baholandi. PubMed, Scopus, Web of Science, Cochrane Library orqali keng qamrovli MEDLINE qidiruvi o'tkazildi. Tadqiqotlarning aksariyati noaniq xavfga ega edi. MD uchun xavf nisbati bo'yicha guruhlar o'rtasida farq yo'q (xavf darajasi = 0,99; 95% ishonch oralig'i [CI] = 0,74-1,33); GZ intensivligi (standartlashtirilgan o'rtacha farq [SMD] = 0,04; 95% CI = 0,79-0,70); rang birliklarida rang o'zgarishi (CPC - 0,04; 95% CI = 0,50-0,42); ΔE^* (CRR = 0,41 (95% CI = 0,07-0,89)) va gingival tirnash xususiyati darajasi (CRR = 1,05; 95% CI = 0,81-1,36) da rang o'zgarishi. O'rtacha deb baholangan GBM xavfi bundan mustasno dalillar sifati, boshqa barcha natijalar pastdan juda pastgacha GBM deb baholandi, rangning o'zgarishi va gingival tirnash xususiyati guruhlar o'rtasida o'xshash edi, ammo bu natijalar uchun dalillarning sifati past yoki juda past deb baholandi, bu esa kasallik darajasini pasaytirdi. bu natijalarga ishonch. , lekin bu natijalar uchun dalillar sifati past yoki juda past deb baholandi, bu esa natijalarning haqiqiyligini pasaytirdi.

Kalit so'zlar: yuqori sezuvchanlik, oqartirish, oqartirish, karbamid peroksid, desensibilizatsiya, karbamid peroksid, desensibilizatsiya qiluvchi jellar.

Introduction. Over the past 10 years, there has been an increased demand for aesthetic dentistry in the dental field. Some popular magazines suggest that whiter teeth make smiles more attractive and increase people's self-esteem [1]. Currently, two methods of teeth whitening under the supervision of a dentist are available: whitening at home [3-5] and whitening in the doctor's office [6-8]. Although studies show the safety and efficacy of both methods [7,9-11], clinicians still face a side effect of the procedure - the effect of postoperative tooth hypersensitivity (DZ) during whitening procedures.

Unfortunately, this side effect is very common. Studies have shown that whitening-induced GC affects 67% to 100% of participants who have had in-office whitening [6,7,12-14] and 37% to 90% of participants who have had home whitening done [3- 5,10,15-18].

Evaluating individual patient data from 11 clinical trials involving bleaching, these authors reported that the risk of GD with in-office bleaching using 35% hydrogen peroxide (HP) solution was (62.9%; 95% confidence). range 56.0–67.3) and for home bleaching using 10% to 16% carbamide peroxide (UA) solution (51%; 95% CI 41.4–60.6) were very similar. On the other hand, GC intensity varied greatly between bleaching protocols. On a pain scale from 0 (no pain) to 4 (very severe pain), the overall average bleaching-induced GI intensity for office whitening was 2.8 ± 2.9 , while home whitening patients reported a sensitivity of 0.5 ± 0.9 . This makes the at-home whitening procedure the most recommended protocol. [20-22].

The presence of GZ has prompted some researchers to evaluate methods to minimize or even eliminate GZ caused by the bleaching procedure. Recently evaluated methods include reducing the concentration and exposure time of the bleaching agent [9,23–25], the use of topical desensitizing agents during bleaching [25–27], and the administration of systemic drugs [12,28].

Topical application of desensitizing agents appears to be an effective strategy for reducing GC in both home bleaching [16,26] and office bleaching. To reduce application time, some manufacturers include some desensitizing agents such as potassium nitrate and sodium fluoride in whitening gels so that the additional step of applying a desensitizing gel can be eliminated.

Several studies have investigated the effectiveness of whitening gels containing desensitizers in reducing whitening-induced GERD, while the available studies report conflicting results. Some authors have reported a reduction in bleach-induced GB with desensitizer-containing gels [5,7,9,14], while others have reported no significant difference between bleaching gels with and without desensitizers. [22]

In light of this, the aim of this systematic review of the literature was to answer the following question: is it consistent with the statement that the risk and intensity of HC in adult patients after a teeth whitening procedure is lower when using desensitizers.

Methods and Materials:

Sources of information and search strategy.

We assessed the risk and intensity of GC during teeth whitening, measured using a visual analogue scale (VAS) and a numerical rating scale (NRS) during and up to 24 hours after teeth whitening (i.e., the period during which patients are more likely to GZ). Color change in color scale units (CHR) and ΔE (CIEL*a*b* system) and risk of gum sensitivity were also assessed as secondary outcomes.

The following electronic databases were used to identify eligible studies: The Cochrane Library, MEDLINE via PubMed, EMBASE. The following citation databases were also searched: Scopus and Web of Science. The reference lists of all primary studies were searched for additional relevant publications and links to relevant articles of each primary study in the PubMed database. There were no restrictions on publication date or languages.

Acceptance Criteria.

Parallel and separate randomized clinical trials were included that compared the risk and intensity of GZ in office and home teeth whitening in adult patients of any age group. Randomized clinical trials were excluded if: 1) the studies evaluated the effects of topical desensitizing agents containing potassium nitrate and/or sodium fluoride; 2) both study groups did not participate in the

studies; or 3) studies included both groups but did not compare whitening gels with equivalent concentrations.

Data were extracted using individual extraction forms, which included details of study methods, design and conditions, age and gender of participants, details of bleaching protocol, bleaching agent, and type of desensitizing gel added to included studies. When data were provided for multiple bleaching sessions, an average value was calculated for each bleaching protocol. When evaluating color change, data was used that represented the most immediate result (up to 3 months after bleaching). When more than one whitening agent from the same group was included in the study, their values were pooled to produce one entry.

The data was analyzed using Revman 5 (Review Manager Version 5, The Cochrane Collaboration, Copenhagen, Denmark). The data from the respective studies were either dichotomous (absolute risk of GBM and gingival irritation) or continuous (GBM intensity, Δ SGU and Δ E). The results were summarized by calculating the standardized mean difference for continuous data and the hazard ratio with 95% confidence interval (CI).

Random effect models were used. Heterogeneity was assessed using the Cochran Q test and I² statistics. All analyzes were performed using Revman 5 (Review Manager Version 5, The Cochrane Collaboration, Copenhagen, Denmark). Subgroup analysis was not performed. Sensitivity analyzes were also performed to investigate the reasons for the high heterogeneity in detection.

Four of the eight studies used only the VAS to assess pain [22], two studies used only the NRS pain scale [14], and one study used both the VAS and the NRS. Research by Browning et al. did not assess the intensity of pain.

Color change was assessed in five studies using colors [22] and in two studies using objective color measuring instruments (spectrophotometer or colorimeter). [14,22] The number of patients per cohort in these studies ranged from 16 to 60. The mean age of all clinical trial participants was approximately 32.1 years. [14]. In three of the eight articles, the majority of participants were women. Two studies had a similar sex distribution,[22] and three studies did not report this information.[14]

When considering the whitening protocol, all studies performed whitening at home. Five of the seven studies used CP alone [14], while the remainder used CP and PV at appropriate concentrations [22]. The concentrations of bleaching products ranged from 10% to 35% for CP. and from 3.5% to 14% for PV. The time of use also varied. CP products were used from 30 minutes to night, while PV products were used from 30 minutes to 3 hours, once or twice a day. The total number of days patients used the gel ranged from 12 days to 4 weeks.

Risk of tooth sensitivity

This result was reported in four studies. [22] The hazard ratio was 0.99 with 95% CI 0.74 to 1.33 ($p=0.95$). The data were not heterogeneous (χ^2 test: $p=0.74$; $I^2=0\%$; Figure 3), meaning that all studies included in the analysis had an overall effect size.

Intensity of tooth sensitivity

This analysis was based on three studies reporting this stimulus outcome. Although Navarra et al. [14] reported data on GZ intensity, their values were not pooled with other studies in the meta-analysis as this was the only study. The standardized mean difference was -0.04 (95% CI = -0.79 to 0.70) with no significant difference in GI intensity between foods ($p = 0.91$). The data were heterogeneous (χ^2 test: $p=0.006$; $I^2=81\%$).

Color change in Δ SGU.

This analysis was based on four studies reporting this information. [22,35,36,38] The standardized mean difference was -0.04 (95% CI = -0.50 to 0.42), which showed no difference in color change between groups ($p = 0.87$). The data were heterogeneous (χ^2 test: $p=0.05$; $I^2=61\%$).

Color change in Δ E*.

This analysis was based on only two studies reporting relevant data.[14,22] The standardized mean difference was 0.41 (95% CI = -0.07 to 0.89), indicating no difference between groups ($p=0.10$). The data were heterogeneous (χ^2 test: $p=0.60$; $I^2=0\%$).

Risk of gum irritation.

This analysis was based on four studies reporting this information. 22,35,78,79 The hazard ratio was 1.05 (95% CI = 0.81–1.36), showing no significant difference between groups ($p = 0.95$). The data were not heterogeneous (χ^2 test: $p=0.74$; $I^2=0\%$).

Sensitivity analysis.

The study by Browning et al³⁵ did not report the standard deviation (SD) of the mean for Δ SGU, so a standard deviation corresponding to 1/3 of the mean was arbitrarily used. This decision was based on analysis of the coefficient of variation from other studies. Sensitivity analysis showed that changing the standard deviation for the extremes and removing the study from the meta-analysis would not change the conclusions. A sensitivity analysis was performed to identify any study responsible for the high heterogeneity in the meta-analysis of CG intensity and color change for both instruments. No studies were found responsible for this heterogeneity.

No difference was found between the gels with and without desensitizers when considering gum sensitivity, which was already expected, since no component of the bleaching gel is able to neutralize the action of peroxides in soft tissues.

Thus, the hypothesis about the equality of materials with respect to GB cannot be rejected. This is the only outcome for which the quality of the evidence was considered moderate. However, it should be kept in mind that the quality of the evidence for the results of discoloration, GB intensity, and risk of gingival irritation was rated as low to very low. This lowering of the level of evidence for these results was the result of a small number of studies due to a lack of information in the primary studies. For example, three out of eight studies reported GC intensity in a similar manner, and only two out of eight studies reported a color change in delta-E. Confidence intervals, with estimates already derived from studies with unclear risk of bias.

In this regard, more rigorous home bleaching methodology should be pursued using gels with and without desensitizers. Although the current research strategy included in-home and in-office whitening, only home whitening studies were found and included in this systematic review of the literature, indicating the need for future studies to compare in-office whitening methods with and without desensitizing gels.

Conclusion.

The inclusion of desensitizers in home whitening gels did not reduce the risk of HC; the quality of the evidence for this outcome was considered moderate. For other outcomes (GZ intensity, discoloration, and gingival irritation), there were no differences between the groups, although the quality of the evidence for these results was low or very low. This indicates that more RCTs with larger sample sizes and rigorous methodology are needed to confirm these results.

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